

Computer Controlled Local Anaesthesia Delivery (CCLAD) System Wand®STA, SleeperOne®, Dentapen® - Electronically Programmed Injection Devices; A Cutting Edge Technology for Painless Dental Anesthesia - A Mini Review

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ABSTRACT:

Local anesthesia is an integral part of dentistry, which is mandatory before operative dental procedures. But it may itself cause pain at the time of needle prick and delivery of anesthetic solution. Computer controlled Local anesthesia delivery (CCLAD) systems like Dentapen®, Wand® STA, SleeperOne® are multi-speed, electronic injection device that adapts to a technique for controlled anesthetic injections for painless anesthesia. The device offers better comfort to patients by minimizing pain and elimination of fear of injection. The system helps the dentists to avoid muscle strain caused by repeated manual injections. It has some certain advantages like automatic priming at onset of device and auto-aspiration to locate the accurate injection site; thus obliterates the chances of hematoma formation and trismus. The CCLAD systems continuously monitor the pressure applied at the injection site to avoid over pressure which is inherent to manual injection which causes pain. They adapt the injection flow accordingly up to the optimum measurement of anesthetic dose which is processed by advanced control algorithms in order to deliver a smooth injection flow. CCLADs are especially suited for pediatric dentistry. The different modes and speeds allow the injection almost unnoticeable and nonthreatening which eliminates the apprehension of the patient, those are usually phobic to conventional injection prick.

Keywords: Computer Controlled Local Anesthesia Delivery (CCLAD), Local anesthesia (LA), Dynamic Pressure Sensing (DPS), Auto-aspiration, Infiltration, Nerve block anesthesia, Intraligamentary injection.

Suggested Citation: N.K. Ghoshal, S. Singh, "Computer Controlled Local Anaesthesia Delivery (CCLAD) System Wand® STA, SleeperOne®, Dentapen® Electronically Programmed Injection Devices. A Cutting Edge Technology for Painless Dental Anesthesia - A Mini Review," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 1(1), pp. 14-19, Nov-Dec 2023. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2023.1\(1\).02](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2023.1(1).02)

INTRODUCTION

Skillful and painless treatment procedure is the basic principle of pediatric dentistry. The patient attitude and cooperation completely depends on it. The child is very sensitive to the unpleasant sensations in the dental chair which determines the future approach of the patient while carrying out the treatment procedure. Fear of dental treatment specifically of injection prick is the commonest thing among the pediatric patients which affects 11% to 65% of children. [1] This psychological condition abstains them to cooperate during the procedure. Many pharmacological and non-pharmacological behavioral managements are there to eliminate the negative attitude of the child (e.g distracting the child, tell show do technique, modelling, injection in camouflaged syringe). Local anesthesia (LA) plays a pivotal role in most of the dental procedure which alleviate the pain during the treatment phase allowing the dentist to perform the procedure. [2] Although LA is administered

in order to eliminate pain while carrying out the procedure, traditional techniques of administration (infiltration, field block, nerve block and intraligamental) are painful for the patients which arise apprehension and noncooperation in pediatric patients at dental office.

However, paradoxically pediatric patients apprehend of the pain of LA injections more than pain during the dental procedure. Fear and anxiety related behaviour impede the proper dental care of children which leads to dental office phobia which is the most challenging situation managing the patients with 'Nursing bottle caries' or early childhood caries (ECC). Computer controlled local anesthesia delivery (CCLAD) recently finds a way out to overcome the problem as the system offers a precise painless pressure controlled injection of local anesthesia (LA) at a programmed regular flow rate which enhances the treatment quality delivered to the pediatric dental patients by obliteration of fear of intraoral injection. [3]

CURRENT SCENARIO OF INJECTION PAIN MANAGEMENT

Despite of careful LA administration local anesthesia in oral mucosa causes pain because of multiple factors like local tissue injury due to needle penetration, pressure, temperature, low pH of LA and their chemical composition. Several techniques have been introduced to minimize the pain of needle penetration into the tissue and pain at the time of deposition of LA like distraction method, topical anesthesia, warming the anesthetic solution, buffering of anesthetic agent, regulation of injection rate, counter irritation and local pre-cooling with refrigerant spray etc. Among the techniques, topical anesthetic gel/spray is regarded as the most popular method. [4, 5]

WHAT IS COMPUTER CONTROLLED LOCAL ANAESTHESIA DELIVERY (CCLAD) SYSTEM?

Computer controlled local anesthesia delivery system is a computerized device which delivers anesthetic solution in an accurate location with optimum pressure and at a controlled slow rate, thus negligible pain perception is elicited which in turn abolishes the odontophobia of the apprehensive patients. So, a comprehensive dental procedure can be performed atraumatically with complete cooperativeness of the patient.

CCLADs have certain features which is preferred to conventional injection technique:

1. Dynamic Pressure Sensing (DPS) Technology

The dynamic pressure sensing monitors the release pressure of LA for the optimal needle position at the time of administration. Audio-visual feedback generated from the device helps in the identification of the correct location for the injection thus minimizes the chances of muscle strain and hematoma formation. [6]

2. Computer Controlled Flow Rate

These devices have an automatic programmed control on the flow rate of anesthetic solution which regulates the drug delivery at the site of injection during administration. It delivers LA at a precise and consistent rate below the patient's pain threshold level. Consistent flow enhances injection predictability. 3 speeds tailored flow rate are there for each injection type

- a. ControlFlo
- b. RapidFlo
- c. TurboFlo

3. Less stress, Better Feedback and Cooperation

The device has an unique pen like grasp, light weighed, least traumatic and permits to perform procedures smoothly.[7]

4. Auto-Aspirate

Accurate aspiration at the exact location at the exact location of the needle. [8]

5. Increased Productivity

For the precision and accurate site delivery the onset of action of LA is very rapid which allows the dentist to start the procedure immediately. A 'comfort fee' can generate revenue. [9]

WAND® STA SYSTEM [10, 11, 12]

The Wand® STA system is one of the leading CCLAD system builds practices by greatly enhancing patient comfort and satisfaction and also compliance of the dentists. The following features makes the system incredible-

1. A unique pen grasp, light unparalleled tactile control. Performs all traditional injection techniques
2. STA enables bi-lateral mandibular treatment in one visit.
3. Can perform newly defined palatal injections (AMSA and P-ASA) painlessly producing unparalleled effectiveness and eliminates anxiety and stress of dental operative procedure.
4. Computer regulated flow rates (Tailored flow rate)
5. DPS technology- enables successful, virtually painless single tooth anesthesia with no collateral numbness
6. Audio-visual feedback aids the accurate location of intralingamentary injection site
7. Enables bi-rotational insertion technique which eliminates the chance of needle deflection
8. It has a multi-cartridge mood which can use multiple cartridges with a single puncture; i.e. especially beneficial for inferior alveolar nerve block (IANB)
9. Auto-aspirate mood allows the exact placement of needle, no retraction mood like syringe
10. Audible feedback aids to learn and assist the junior dentists at training mood.

Figure 1. Wand® STA System

DENTAPEN® (SEPTODENT, SWITZERLAND) [12, 13]

Dentapen® is a new, cable less motorized syringe system that has grown popularity because of less technique sensitiveness and ease of operation. The special features of Dentapen® are:

1. Light (50 gm), cordless and battery operated intuitive device. No console, no foot control and no tubing.
2. Operational in seconds; auto priming at the onset of device

3. Intellectual auto-aspiration mood enables correct injection location
4. Dentapen® micro compressor continuously monitors the pressure applied to the tissue of the injection site and adjusts the flow of anesthetic accordingly. 3 injection speeds for better administration of LA; Fast 1 mL/30s, Medium 1mL/60s and Slow 1mL/90s. The high quality gears and engine components are similar to ones used in swiss luxury atch industry.
5. The high performance of lithium batteries enables Dentapen® to function at optimum level to complete continuous calculations to execute a perfect infection. With unparalleled power Dentapen® can push up to 13 kg of force which is 260 times of its own weight.
6. Two different handles allow to hold more like a traditional syringe by the wings and pen like grasp
7. Compatible with the standard anesthetic cartridges.
8. Cost effectiveness and hygienic; provided with fully autoclavable accessories and single use protective sleeves.

Figure 2. Dentapen®

Figure 3. Difference in pain sensation: conventional injection and Dentapen®

SLEEPERONE® [14, 15]

SleeperOne® is a digitally controlled local anesthetic system which has a unique high tech design looks nothing like a manual syringe which is equipped with same features of precision and programmed LA delivery system like other CCLADs. The features are discussed below-

1. The unlikeliness of syringe offers friendly appearance which reassures children and after the first injection they know that is a 'magic pen' which is completely painless
2. Pen grip enables the dentist to position the fingers close to the needle allowing more support points to perform with maximum precision
3. Reduce RSI (Repetitive strain injury) - the dentist no longer needs to apply pressure to the syringe to deliver the anesthetic as it is electronically programmed with a certain continuous speed of release of LA with a minimal pressure below the pain threshold level at the injection site.
4. Most effective system to deliver intalingamental, palatal, block, infiltration and even intraosseous anesthesia in children without altering the workflow
5. Very light (71 g) for easy and comfortable handling; also enhances the visibility of the operating field.
6. Facilitating pain-free penetration and reduced penetration depth, SleeperOne's patented needles suppress pain because of their unique bevel, which acts like a scalpel blade so that the tissues are no longer torn but incised.
7. A mark is present on the hub for correct orientation that they can be inserted more shallowly to avoid painful contact with periosteum unlike conventional needles.

Figure 4. SleeperOne®

CONCLUSION

CCLADs have certain advantages over conventional injections like anxiolysis, increased patient cooperation, precision, minimal pressure, predictability, rapid onset of action, quick regain of sensation and thus least chances of cheek and lip biting of child, ability to work on multiple sites at the same visit, localized numbness, suitable in all types of oral anesthesia targeted tooth anesthesia etc. In spite of the myriads of merits CCLADs also have some of the shortcomings like high price, technique sensitivity, unsuitable for long duration operative procedures and learning curve associated with use. Keeping in mind of the merits and demerits of CCLAD are more preferable in dentistry; specially in pedodontics but issues like availability, learning curve and expense indicate that more research in the respective field is necessary whether the conventional syringe should be substituted by CCLADs in near future or not.

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